

Between Economic Ties and Their Political Instrumentalisation

The Case of Optants, Seasonal Workers, and Commuters from the Hlučín Region in Interwar Germany*

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This study focuses primarily on former residents (optants) of the Hlučín region, on its residents who were employed in Germany (commuters and seasonal workers), and on the work of German irredentists among them, in the interwar period. Hlučín inhabitants in Germany were crucial for the irredentist movement in influencing the situation in the Hlučín region. Functionaries of the Reichsverband heimatliebender Hultschiner were aware of the importance of arranging employment opportunities for maintaining the influence in the Hlučín region. Hlučín optants, commuters, and seasonal workers were expected to support Germanness in the Hlučín region in exchange for securing living.

Keywords *Central Europe; Hlučín Region; Interwar Period; Labour Migration; Czech–German Relations; Irredentist Movement*

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The Decision to Separate the Hlučín Region from Germany and the Rise of German Irredentist Activities

By a decision of the Treaty of Versailles, the southern part of the Upper Silesian district of Ratibor (today Racibórz in Poland) was assigned to the newly established state of Czechoslovakia. This was the only part of Prussian Silesia inhabited by a population speaking a Czech dialect; however, this population did not welcome the separation from Germany and accepted the affiliation to the new state coolly, if not negatively. The handover of 36 municipalities from German to Czechoslovak sovereignty took place on 4 February 1920. As the traditional centre of the region, Ratibor, remained in Germany, Hlučín became the new administrative centre. This is how the region of Hlučín (*Hlučínsko*) came into being. Following a decision of the delimitation commission, two

* This study was conducted as part of the project Migration and Us: Mobility, Refugees, and Borders from the Perspective of the Humanities [CZ.02. 01. 01/00/23_025/0008741], supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth, and Sports of the Czech Republic, as part of the Jan Amos Komenský Operational Program (OP JAK), cofinanced by the European Union.

additional municipalities were incorporated into the Hlučín region in March 1923.¹

Immediately after information about possible separation of a part or all of the Ratibor region from German Upper Silesia leaked out of the peace conference negotiations, a group of individuals formed in the Ratibor region who influenced public opinion in a pro-German direction. Following the decision of the peace conference, they strove for the return of the lost territory to Germany. Therefore, this group actively supported German cultural, associational, and political activities in the Hlučín region in various ways. Its members were mainly drawn from teachers and public servants who had already worked there prior to 1920. The Hlučín irredentist movement² found its principal organiser in Dr Reinhold Weigel,³ originally a teacher at the pedagogic secondary school (*Lehreranstalt*) in Ratibor. Weigel worked in the Ratibor region in the early 1920s as a commissioner for immigrants and optants from the Hlučín region, for whom he established the *Schutzstelle für Optanten aus dem Hultschiner Ländchen* (Protective Office for Optants from the Hlučín Region). In 1923, he was appointed as a senior official in the Presidium of the Provincial Government in Oppeln (today Opole in Poland). In October 1927, he was promoted there to head of the education department.

Weigel's activities were crucial to the emergence of the key support of the irredentist movement, the association known as the Reich League of Patriotic Hlučín Inhabitants (*Reichsverband Heimatliebender Hultschiner*; hereafter RHH). The activities of the RHH were overtly anti-Czechoslovak, as the association did not conceal its endeavour to reintegrate the Hlučín region into Germany. The most important local branches of the RHH operated in Ratibor, Gleiwitz (today Gliwice), and Vratislav (Wrocław). Other local branches were established, inter alia, in Hindenburg (Zabrze), Berlin, Bottrop, Gladbeck, Waldenburg (Wałbrzych), and Beuthen (Bytom).⁴ The RHH influenced public opinion in the Hlučín region mainly through optants, who moved to Germany (and who maintained family and social ties in their native region), as well as through inhabitants of the Hlučín region working in Germany. The association played an important role in the placement and employment of optants, seasonal workers, and commuters from the Hlučín region in Germany. Hlučín inhabitants had already worked in large numbers in German Silesia and other German areas prior to the war, i.e. at a time when they were citizens of the German Empire, and continued to do so after 1920, when they were separated from Germany.⁵

Weigel served as the contact person for the Hlučín region within the *Deutsche Stiftung*,

¹ NEMINÁŘ, Jiří: Přisouzení Československu : 100 let od připojení Hati a Piště. *Slezský sborník* 121, 2023, 1, pp. 32–57.

² I do not use the term *irredentism* in a negative sense, but as a neutral designation for situations in which a particular state demands to gain areas of another state where the inhabitants' linguistic or cultural affiliation is not fully identifiable with the state of which they are citizens. This was precisely the position of the Hlučín region in the interwar period in relation to Czechoslovakia and Germany.

³ DOKOUPIL, Lumír – MYŠKA, Milan (eds.): *Biografický slovník Slezska a severní Moravy*, 5. Opava – Ostrava 1996, p. 134; KRAVAR, Zdeněk – NEMINÁŘ, Jiří: Osobní fond Reinholda Weigela. *Hlučínsko : vlastivědný časopis Muzea Hlučínska* 7, 2017, 2, pp. 25–26.

⁴ KLADIWA, Pavel: Nelitostný soubor. Der treudeutsche Hultschiner a další periodika v boji o přízeň hlučínského obyvatelstva od připojení Hlučínska k ČSR do roku 1930. *Slezský sborník* 122, 2024, 2, pp. 148–170, here pp. 150–151; SOMMER, Karel: Proněmecké irredentistické hnutí na Hlučínsku v první polovině 20. let. *Slezský sborník* 90, 1992, 3–4, pp. 227–241, here p. 228.

⁵ The social and economic situation in the Hlučín region after its separation from Germany was addressed by Leo Dubowy and Paul Miketta in their doctoral theses. Both of them were natives of the Hlučín region. DUBOWÝ, Leo: *Die sozialen Verhältnisse im Hultschiner Ländchen*. Breslau 1922; MIKETTA, Paul: *Die wirtschaftlichen Verhältnisse des Hultschiner Ländchens*. Breslau 1922.

a semi-state foundation established to promote Germanness in territories that Germany was compelled to cede after the First World War. It virtually functioned as a covert office of the German government and, after 1933, provided its resources to construct fifth columns in the ceded territories.⁶ Weigel thus acted as an intermediary between the RHH and the *Deutsche Stiftung*. From 1926 onwards, the RHH formed part of the Eastern Committee – a working association of eastern organisations united in the German Protective League (*Ostausschuss – Arbeitsgemeinschaft im Deutschen Schutzbund vereinigter Ostverbände*). The League was founded in 1919 as a political and cultural umbrella organisation for all associations and federations promoting Germanness abroad and in the borderlands.

As already mentioned, the topic of the economic dependence of a significant part of the population of the interwar Hlučín region on the German labour market is not unknown in historiography.⁷ The author of syntheses about the Hlučín region, Vilém Plaček, necessarily had to deal with it;⁸ Karel Sommer's study paid attention directly to the activities of the pro-German irredentists in the Hlučín region,⁹ but only for the first half of the 1920s. The ambition of this study is to present the topic as comprehensively as possible. Therefore, it draws not only on archival fonds of Czechoslovak state authorities (the Ministry of the Interior in Prague, the Provincial Office in Brno, the Police Directorate in Moravská Ostrava) and the estate of the head of the RHH, R. Weigel, but also on statistical data from Czechoslovak censuses, as well as German archival fonds, especially the *Deutsche Stiftung* stored in the Federal Archives (Bundesarchiv) in Berlin-Lichterfelde.

The Dependence of a Large Number of Inhabitants of the Hlučín Region on Job Opportunities in Germany as a Basic Advantage for the German Irredentists

The availability of employment opportunities within the Hlučín region itself was far from sufficient. The region was predominantly agrarian, with little industry; the largest local employers were two coal mines in Petřkovice. Nor did agriculture provide adequate employment for a demographically growing population, as a result of the modernisation of large estates. Precisely because of the severe shortage of work at home, both temporary and permanent extensive labour migration from the region emerged from the second half of the nineteenth century (bricklayers, miners, industrial and agricultural labourers, itinerant traders) and continued also after the war. Two major industrial areas were located in close proximity to the Hlučín region: Upper Silesia and Ostrava–Karviná. In the final pre-war years, approximately 3,500 individuals left the region in search of work in various parts of Germany (bricklayers, carpenters, roofers, itinerant traders, herdsmen).¹⁰ Hlučín workers were employed in large numbers in mines of Prussian Upper Silesia (the Rybník, Kattowitz/Katowice, and Beuthen/Bytom regions). In Westphalian Bottrop, around

⁶ The permanent staff of the *Deutsche Stiftung* itself was very small, which clearly indicates that its operational agenda was handled by government authorities. GIERSCHE, Reinhard: *Deutsche Stiftung*. In: FRICKE, Dieter (ed.): *Lexikon zur Parteigeschichte 1789–1945*, 2. Leipzig 1983–1986, pp. 359–366.

⁷ An overview of the literature on the modern history of the Hlučín region is provided in the introduction to KLADIWA, P.: *Nelitostný soubor*.

⁸ PLAČEK, Vilém: *Prajzáci aneb k osudům Hlučínska 1742–1960*. Hlučín 2000; PLAČEK, Vilém: *Prajzáci 2, aneb, Hlučínsko ve staronové vlasti 1920–1938*. Háj ve Slezsku 2007.

⁹ SOMMER, K.: *Proněmecké irredentistické hnutí*, pp. 227–241.

¹⁰ PLAČEK, Vilém: *Připojení Hlučínska k ČSR dne 4. února 1920*. In: *Hlučínsko v proměnách času*. Hlučín 1995, pp. 27–39, here p. 35. No reference is provided to the source used by Plaček.

500 families from the Hlučín region were living at the beginning of the 20th century; in this case, the migration clearly took the form of permanent resettlement.¹¹

A specific group consisted of itinerant traders (*Hausierer*). Itinerant trading originated in the Hlučín municipality of Deutsch Krawarn (today Kravaře) in the second third of the 19th century, when a growing population sought means of livelihood. The traders set out in spring and returned in autumn. At the beginning of the year, itinerant traders procured their stock; at that time, around one hundred traders would gather in the inns of Deutsch Krawarn, where haberdashery goods were displayed in inn halls – mainly small consumer items such as combs, brushes, buttons, needles, knives, as well as inexpensive luxury goods including rings, bracelets, chains, purses, and mirrors. Small printed images were also sold, as well as textiles, and household goods such as cutlery, soap, and stomach drops. Itinerant traders reached their sales territories by railway, and some travelled by horse-drawn carts. Along the way, they stopped in locations where they purchased goods (notably Breslau, Dresden, Berlin, and earlier also Posen/Poznań). After selling their merchandise, they returned to these purchasing centres to replenish their supplies. In the meantime, following visits to individual villages, they would return to a location roughly in the centre of their sales area, where they stored smaller reserves of goods, for example with a local innkeeper. In Deutsch Krawarn prior to the First World War, the number of annual itinerant trading licences ranged between 400 and 500.¹²

As early as the German period, a certain number of Hlučín inhabitants worked in the Ostrava region; however, it is difficult to arrive at precise figures. According to a report by the Ratibor district administrator August Wellenkamp, at the beginning of the 20th century, approximately six thousand workers from the southern part of the Ratibor district (i.e. from the Hlučín region) were employed in Austrian industrial enterprises. The report is somewhat ambiguous as it uses the phrase *Austrian industrial enterprises* rather than *industrial enterprises in Austria* and, within a single sentence, mentions the Petřkovice mines and Austrian enterprises in Přívoz, Moravská Ostrava, and Vítkovice. It appears likely that by the term *Austrian industrial enterprises* the author also meant the Petřkovice mines in the Hlučín region, since their owner was the Vítkovice Coal Mines, an Austrian company.¹³ As the Petřkovice mines employed approximately 2,500 people, this would leave around 3,500 male and female workers from the Hlučín region commuting to work in the Ostrava region. Given the proximity of the south-eastern part of the Hlučín region and the transport accessibility of the entire southern part of the region via the Opava–Svinov railway line, which until 1920, ran on the Austrian side along the state border with the Prussian Hlučín region, it appears plausible that many people commuted to the Ostrava region. Unfortunately, no precise statistics are available, and we are therefore reliant on this isolated and unverifiable estimate. It seems that by the end of the Prussian period, the number of Hlučín inhabitants working in the Ostrava region had declined significantly. This

¹¹ *Katolické noviny pro lid moravský v Pruském Slezsku*, 12 December 1904, p. 3. According to another report a few years later, there were allegedly about 1,000 Moravians from the Hlučín region in Bottrop. See VYHLÍDAL, Jan: *Pod perutěmi pruského orla : Obrázky ze života českého lidu v Prusku*. Opava 1910, p. 82.

¹² Die geschichtliche Entwicklung des Hausier-Handels in Deutsch-Krawarn. *Treudeutscher Hultschiner*, July 1924, pp. 6–8; PETERKOVÁ, Eva: Nová obživa kravařských obyvatel v 19. století. *Hlučínsko : Vlastivědný časopis Muzea Hlučínka* 2, 2012, 2, pp. 5–7.

¹³ Archiwum Państwowe w Opolu, Rejencja Opolska, Acten des Regierungs – Präsidenten zu Oppeln, wydz. I, call. no. 45/1191/0/2/8357.

conclusion is based on the existence of a list of Prussian citizens crossing the border daily in order to work in Ostrava and its surrounding municipalities (i.e. inhabitants of the Hlučín region), which was compiled in 1919, one year before the Hlučín region was incorporated into Czechoslovakia. The list contained 437 persons (including 242 women).¹⁴ It is possible that it does not include all Hlučín inhabitants, as employees of the Vítkovice Ironworks do not appear in it at all. Nevertheless, the disparity between 437 and 3,500 is evident.

In 1919, the largest employer of the still foreign Hlučín inhabitants in the Ostrava region was the Austrian Association for Chemical and Metallurgical Production in Hrušov (173 employees, of whom 134 were women), followed by Himmelbauer's chemical plant in Ostrava-Prívov (47, including 35 women), the František mine (29), the Joint-Stock Company for the Chemical Industry in Prívov (26, including 25 women), the Prívov mineral oil refinery (24, including 16 women), the Hlubina mine on the border between Moravská Ostrava and Vítkovice (23), the Ida mine in Hrušov (22), the Hubert mine in Hrušov (21, including ten women), etc.¹⁵ It appears that as long as employment was available in the Petřkovice mines and in the mines of German Upper Silesia, the number of Hlučín miners seeking work on the opposite bank of the Oder (the border river) was limited, and that it was primarily women who sought employment in the Ostrava region.

Hlučín inhabitants working in factories and mines in the Ostrava region predominantly commuted, although some also relocated. In 1921, 617 of them resided in Moravská Ostrava, Slezská Ostrava, and their suburban municipalities; by 1930, this number had risen to 1,872.¹⁶

According to the results of the 1921 census, 10,035 inhabitants of the Hlučín region were employed in industry and crafts. Of these, 5,850 worked directly within the Hlučín region (including the mines). The remainder – over 4,000 people – must therefore have been economically active elsewhere, in the Ostrava region and especially in Germany.¹⁷ In 1930, the statistics were even worse: 10,996 people¹⁸ earned their living in industry and crafts, but only 5,236 of them (i.e. 47.6%) could find employment within the Hlučín region.¹⁹ Moreover, shortly after this census, the Great Depression struck in full force.

According to the 1921 census, 1,452 persons in the Hlučín region were self-employed in agriculture, while the total number employed in agriculture amounted to 5,437 (including 2,682 women).²⁰ In 1930, the number of self-employed persons in agriculture increased to 2,078, whereas the total number of those employed declined to 4,859.²¹ However, out of 7,669 agricultural farms in the Hlučín region in 1930, 2,196 had an area of up to 0.5 ha and a further 4,481 had an area of up to 5 ha (the average in this group was only 1.8 ha). Such areas were insufficient even to sustain the owner, let alone to employ labourers.²² Consequently, many agricultural workers were unable to find employment

¹⁴ Zemský archiv Opava (ZAO), Policejní ředitelství Moravská Ostrava (PŘMO), box 198, file no. 578/19.

¹⁵ Ibidem.

¹⁶ *Sčítání lidu v Republice československé ze dne 15. února 1921*, III. Praha 1927; *Sčítání lidu v republice Československé ze dne 1. prosince 1930*, III. Praha 1937, p. 48.

¹⁷ *Sčítání lidu v Republice československé ze dne 15. února 1921*, II/2. Praha 1925, p. 11.

¹⁸ *Sčítání lidu v republice Československé ze dne 1. prosince 1930*, II/1. Praha 1934, p. 118.

¹⁹ PLÁČEK, V.: *Prajzáci 2*, p. 156.

²⁰ *Sčítání lidu v Republice československé ze dne 15. února 1921*, II/2. Praha 1925, p. 6.

²¹ *Sčítání lidu v republice Československé ze dne 1. prosince 1930*, II/1. Praha 1934, p. 100.

²² PLÁČEK, V.: *Prajzáci 2*, pp. 162–163.

within the Hlučín region.

The post-war crisis, together with changes in the course of the state border, destabilised the situation, and thousands of Hlučín inhabitants found themselves in a state of existential uncertainty. As a result of the Polish–German conflict in Upper Silesia, approximately 3,000 construction and mining workers from the Hlučín region lost their jobs.²³ The end of the conflict and the delineation of the new Polish–German border did little to improve their situation, as most mines and other industrial enterprises were allocated to Poland.²⁴ Although no comprehensive statistical data are available, partial evidence points to mass dismissals of Hlučín inhabitants from enterprises that fell under Polish control. According to an investigation conducted by Czechoslovak authorities in 1923, in the municipality of Vřesina in the Hlučín region, which had approximately 600 inhabitants, around 60 workers previously employed at the Emma mine near Rybník were affected. Similarly, about 75 miners from the municipality of Hať, with around 1,700 inhabitants, were dismissed from Polish enterprises.²⁵

Labour market conditions were far from favourable in German Silesia and other parts of Germany, which were shaken by post-war disintegration and subsequently by hyperinflation. Nor did the Ostrava–Karviná coal district offer sufficient alternative employment opportunities, since as early as the beginning of the 1920s, Ostrava's mines and industrial enterprises were struggling with sales problems. One of the two mines located directly in the Hlučín region, in Petřkovice, curtailed production owing to the depletion of coal reserves and consequently employed 53% fewer miners in 1937 than in 1919. Production at the other mine was also restricted more severely than at other mines.²⁶ Work was unavailable for thousands of people, even though the population of the Hlučín region declined by more than 4,000 in the early 1920s as a result of opting for Germany (see below).

Unemployment could not be resolved even in the second half of the 1920s, which is nevertheless regarded as the golden era of interwar Czechoslovakia. In March 1926, the mayor of the municipality of Píšť in the Hlučín region, which had 1,700 inhabitants, informed the Plenipotentiary Commissioner of the Czechoslovak Republic for the Hlučín Region, Josef Šrámek, of the catastrophic situation of 128 unemployed men. The majority of them (94) were bricklayers who had worked in Germany since time immemorial but found themselves unemployed owing to the poor state of the labour market there. The mayor explicitly stated that construction firms in Czechoslovakia refused to hire them because they came from the Hlučín region. The enclosed list of names also included 14 carpenters, 16 unspecified labourers, a joiner, a wheelwright, a locksmith, and a miner. Most of them were breadwinners for large families and, as the mayor emphasised, their families were already completely financially exhausted.²⁷

In light of these figures from Píšť, the optimistic report published by *Moravsko-slezský denník* in 1928 does not appear accurate. Referring to official statistics from 1927, the

²³ ZAO, Reinhold Weigel, box 4. On 3 June 1921, Commissioner Weigel wrote to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs in Berlin regarding unemployment in the Hlučín region as a consequence of the Polish uprising in Upper Silesia.

²⁴ For details of the German–Polish conflict and the partition of Upper Silesia, see WILSON, Tim: *Frontiers of Violence: Conflict and Identity in Ulster and Upper Silesia 1918–1922*. Oxford 2010.

²⁵ ZAO, Revírní báňský úřad v Mor. Ostravě, box 554, inv. no. 2098, file no. 9795/23.

²⁶ NOUŠOVÁ Jitka: Postavení hornictva dolů Anselm a Oskar v Ostravě–Petřkovicích v meziválečném období. In: *Ostrava : Sborník příspěvků k dějinám a výstavbě města* 12, 1983, pp. 166–198, here p. 168, 171.

²⁷ ZAO, PŘMO, box 251, call no. 1333, file no. 235, Municipal Office in Píšť to Šrámek on 22 March 1926.

newspaper reported 8,275 workers in the entire Hlučín region, of whom only 632 were unemployed and 960 worked in Germany. In addition, 537 itinerant traders were reportedly working in Germany at that time. The remainder, i.e. the vast majority, were said to be employed in Czechoslovakia, primarily in the Ostrava region.²⁸

During the Great Depression, which struck in full force in 1931, the situation deteriorated sharply. As late as the end of November 1935, there were 3,718 unemployed persons in the Hlučín district.²⁹ The poor economic situation in the Hlučín region contributed to the strengthening of pro-German sentiments.

Optants and Other Migrants from the Hlučín Region. The Work of German Irredentists with them

Under the Treaty of Versailles, the inhabitants of the Hlučín region were granted the right to choose their citizenship freely. They could either accept Czechoslovak citizenship or, within a two-year period (from January 1920 to January 1922), opt for German citizenship. If a married man opted, his decision applied equally to his wife and underage children. Those who opted were obliged to resettle in Germany within twelve months of making their declaration of option.³⁰

Declarations of option were submitted by 4,500 inhabitants, i.e. about one tenth of the population of the Hlučín region. The towns of Hlučín and Kravaře exhibited a markedly above-average proportion of optants.

According to Karel Sommer, the vast majority of Hlučín inhabitants completed the option form for political reasons, while the number of economically motivated optants was allegedly small.³¹ I do not share this view and believe that economic motives played a substantial role. Many optants, probably even the majority, submitted their declarations of option while already in Germany, where they were working or studying.³² When several dozen optants later decided to return to the Hlučín region, they usually stated in justification in their applications for Czechoslovak citizenship that they had virtually been compelled to submit the option declaration by threats from employers that they would otherwise lose their jobs, or from school officials that they would otherwise be unable to continue their studies. Czechoslovak authorities subsequently investigated the reasons why the applicants had opted for Germany. The investigations usually confirmed the reasons stated by the optants (i.e. economic motives combined with agitation and threats of dismissal from employment in Germany). However, the investigating gendarme sometimes regarded it as an aggravating circumstance that the optant had remained in Germany while employed, but returned home solely for material reasons after the termination of that employment.³³ This was, moreover, corroborated by the more candid confessions of some

²⁸ *Moravsko-slezský denník*, 4 October 1928, p. 1.

²⁹ PLÁČEK, V.: *Prajzáci* 2, p. 199.

³⁰ KLADIWA, Pavel: *Odvolané opce : Snahy optantů z Hlučínska o (znovu)nabytí čs. státního občanství*. In: *Hlučínsko 1920–2020 : sborník příspěvků z konference ke 100. výročí vzniku Hlučínska*. Hlučín 2020 pp. 48–57.

³¹ SOMMER, K.: *Proněmecké irredentistické hnutí*, p. 234.

³² For example, in the municipality of Bobrovníky, only six out of 37 optants were present at the time of the census (February 1921). BIELOSCHKOVÁ, Lucie: *Několik fragmentů dějin meziválečného Hlučínska*. Unpublished bachelor's thesis. Ostrava 2021, p. 17.

³³ KLADIWA, P.: *Odvolané opce*, pp. 48–57.

optants. Even such conduct, however, was motivated primarily by economic considerations.

Tab. 1: The number and the proportion of optants in the population of the Hlučín region

Municipality in the Hlučín region	Number of optants ³⁴	Proportion of optants in the population (%)
Antošovice	20	6.0
Bělá	5	1.1
Bobrovniky	37	6.7
Bohuslavice	81	6.9
Bolatice	136	5.7
Darkovice	79	8.0
Darkovičky	48	5.5
Dolní Benešov	228	12.0
Hlučín	748	15.6
Hněvošice	31	4.9
Hošťálkovic	71	6.1
Chlebičov	33	4.9
Chuchelná	118	11.6
Kobeřice	98	5.3
Koblov	79	5.0
Kouty	140	8.9
Kozmice	66	5.9
Kravaře	804	18.4
Lhotka	53	5.5
Ludgeřovice	284	8.7
Malé Hoštice	55	5.2
Markvartovice	48	4.0
Oldřšov	110	8.0
Petřkovice	260	10.0
Rohov	83	11.7
Služovice	58	13.4
Strahovice	48	6.8
Sudice	95	9.5
Šilheřovice	203	12.9
Štěpánkovice	111	6.1
Třebom	63	8.3
Vrbka	3	1.7
Velké Hoštice	72	5.7
Vřesina	43	7.0
Zábřeh	70	11.1
Závada	54	11.7
Hlučín region in total	4,535	9.4

Optants who resettled in Germany only after submitting their option, i.e. during the relocation period granted following the submission of the declaration, crossed the

³⁴ Státní okresní archiv Opava, fonds Okresní úřad Hlučín, inv. no. 1. Number of optants according to the list of names for individual municipalities. If deletions in the lists are also taken into account, the total figure would amount to 4,527. The municipalities of Hař and Pišť were not yet part of the Hlučín region at that time. The proportion of the population was calculated on the basis of: *Statistický lexikon obcí na Moravě a ve Slezsku*. Praha 1924, pp. 114–115.

border between the Hlučín region and German Silesia at a time when state and municipal authorities there were already overwhelmed with providing for refugees from areas that ultimately fell to Poland after the three Upper Silesian uprisings. The bleak social situation of immigrants from the Polish part of Upper Silesia was described in alarming terms by the Central Office for the Care of Silesian Refugees (*Zentralstelle für die schlesische Flüchtlingsfürsorge*).³⁵ According to a report by the German Red Cross dated 12 February 1923, optants from the Hlučín region were materially more demanding than Upper Silesian refugees, who had been forced to flee under threat to their lives and without receiving assistance.³⁶

A distinct group of migrants from the Hlučín region consisted of teachers from the Prussian period. Around the time of the handover of the Hlučín region to Czechoslovakia, a survey was conducted to determine how teaching staff intended to respond to the new circumstances. The majority of teachers (87) replied that they would not remain in the Hlučín region and would leave for Germany immediately. Only six declared a firm intention to remain in the service of the new state. Forty-six teachers stated that they would remain in the Czechoslovak school system on a trial basis or for a temporary period, whereas fourteen intended to remain in the service of the new state while receiving paid leave from Germany. Two teachers retired, and one had already been transferred to the German part of the Ratibor region.³⁷

At the beginning of 1922, Weigel complained that the placement of teachers from the Hlučín region was not determined by merit in promoting Germanness, but solely by economic considerations. He stated that out of approximately fifty teachers who had been dismissed from Czechoslovak service but were temporarily remaining in the Hlučín region while receiving salaries from the Prussian government, only a few were actively working to support German organisations in the Hlučín region; nevertheless, the degree of merit in promoting Germanness played no role in appointments to teaching posts in Germany.³⁸

Under Weigel's leadership, the RHH succeeded in gaining or exacting favour among many optants. It both assisted in the Ratibor region with providing for optants who lacked material resources and employment in Germany and built a network of contacts with authorities and employers in various parts of Germany in order to secure employment and accommodation for optants. However, this was not motivated by altruism, as will be shown below.

In early 1922, Weigel sent a proposal to Erich Krahrmer-Möllenberg, the leading official of the *Deutsche Stiftung* in Berlin, outlining plans for the establishment of a German Protective Office (*Deutsche Schutzstelle*). It was intended to serve the Hlučín region, the Těšín region, and the Sudeten areas of Moravia and Silesia, and was to be located in Ratibor

³⁵ SOMMER, K.: *Proněmecké iredentistické hnutí*, p. 233.

³⁶ Bundesarchiv Berlin-Lichterfelde, R 1501/118486, *Fürsorge für Flüchtlinge aus dem Hultschiner Ländchen*, Nov. 1922 - Aug. 1923. Post-war Germany experienced an influx of refugees (Germans from lost territories, Jews, Russians), which worsened an already difficult situation. The number of refugees who settled temporarily or permanently on German soil in the few years between the end of World War I and the onset of the hyperinflation in 1923 is estimated at 1.5 million. The German Red Cross was responsible for a vast network of refugee camps. SAMMARTINO, Annemaria H.: *The Impossible Border: Germany and the East, 1914–1922*. Ithaca – London 2014, pp. 111, 120.

³⁷ ZAO, Reinhold Weigel, box 1. List of teachers from the Ratibor region with their stated intentions to remain or not in the event of a possible incorporation into Czechoslovakia, n.d.

³⁸ *Ibidem*, box 5.

because of its position on the main railway line and its proximity to the border. Weigel considered its tasks to be the establishment of a network of informants in the “served” territories, the creation of an intelligence centre, assistance for expelled Germans, and the promotion of Germanness in the “served” territories (strengthening German economic organisations, arranging employment, establishing associations, maintaining German schools, and providing legal protection for allegedly oppressed Germans through local German lawyers recruited for cooperation).³⁹ It is therefore evident that the principal objective was the promotion of Germanness in the ceded Hlučín region, while optants functioned rather as an instrument. Primary sources from 1922 and 1923 then mention an organisation named *Schutzstelle für die Hultschiner Optanten* (Protective Office for Hlučín Optants), as well as an Advisory Office (*Beratungsstelle*), or Welfare Office (*Fürsorgestelle*). These designations most likely refer to the same organisation.

In his lobbying German administrative authorities, Weigel emphasised the participation of approximately eight hundred Hlučín inhabitants in German units (*Selbstschutz*) during the Upper Silesian uprisings – probably mainly miners and workers employed in the conflict areas.⁴⁰ In May 1922, he complained about what he regarded as an overly rigid stance of the German Red Cross regarding the accommodation of Hlučín optants. Unlike Upper Silesian refugees, the Red Cross did not consider optants to be refugees. Weigel pointed to severe capacity problems in providing short-term accommodation for optants in Ratibor prior to their onward placement in Germany; stables or laundries were often used as temporary lodgings.⁴¹ In November 1922, the Reich⁴² Commissioner for Civilian Prisoners and Refugees, Daniel Stücklen, informed Prussian Prime Minister Otto Braun of the extremely poor conditions experienced by some optants in Ratibor. He reported that families were living in simple wooden huts that were dangerous during storms. At the same time, an empty prison building existed in Ratibor, whose lower rooms were used by the supply office, while the unused upper rooms could be adapted to accommodate at least 100 families. One month later, the Prussian Ministry of Justice agreed to release the premises of the old judicial prison, and by June 1923, the first 26 flats were ready.⁴³

As the deadline for the departure of the remaining optants from the Hlučín region (January 1923) was approaching, German authorities were aware of the heavy burden posed by Upper Silesian refugees. On 1 November 1922, the Reich Minister of Finance⁴⁴ wrote to the Ministry of the Interior, suggesting that the placement of optants might be entrusted to Weigel’s organisation, thereby making maximal use of local capacities in Ratibor. The Minister of the Interior supported his proposal on 5 December 1922. On 9 December 1922, Reich Commissioner Stücklen noted that the organisational provision of assistance would remain in the hands of the Red Cross, which would cooperate closely with the RHH. In fact, Stücklen had already proposed transferring the agenda

³⁹ Bundesarchiv Berlin-Lichterfelde, R 8043/957.

⁴⁰ ZAO, Reinhold Weigel, box 5.

⁴¹ Ibidem.

⁴² The German term *reichs* has a specific meaning that is not conveyed by the English term *imperial*. In this specific context, it refers to a federal commissioner (in Germany, there were both federal offices and the offices of individual German states).

⁴³ Bundesarchiv Berlin-Lichterfelde, R 1501/118486, Fürsorge für Flüchtlinge aus dem Hultschiner Ländchen, Nov. 1922 – Aug. 1923.

⁴⁴ It means Federal Minister of Finance – see footnote 42.

of optants to Weigel's organisation as early as the end of October, noting that his office no longer had any available accommodation capacity in the Ratibor region. The authorities feared the moment when hundreds of additional optants, still residing in the Hlučín region but already working in Ratibor, would arrive.⁴⁵

On 12 January 1923, the German Red Cross noted with relief that, contrary to expectations, Hlučín optants had been granted permission by Czechoslovak authorities to remain temporarily even after 10 January 1923 in order to arrange the sale of their property and settle other matters. There was therefore no frantic exodus, but rather a gradual departure. At that time, twenty Hlučín families and two single individuals were accommodated in barrack housing in Ratibor. The Red Cross highlighted that Weigel had secured employment and housing opportunities for a large number of emigrants, particularly single men, in the Westphalian coal district.⁴⁶ This likely referred to Weigel's agreement with the management of the Ewald mine in Westphalia, which informed him in August 1922 that it could accept a further 200 trained miners, but due to a shortage of housing, only unmarried men could be considered. Weigel immediately replied that, as agreed, he would send 200 trained miners with confirmation from the RHH.⁴⁷

Several primary sources indicate that Weigel expected those inhabitants of the Hlučín region whom he assisted, whether optants or Czechoslovak citizens, to join the RHH and engage with the German cause in the Hlučín region. In the mid-1920s, a Czech gendarmerie station monitoring the activities of the local RHH branch in Waldenburg reported that approximately 52 bricklayers from the Hlučín region were working in the town and that all were required to join the RHH, otherwise they would lose their jobs.⁴⁸

Czechoslovak authorities closely monitored the association. They scrutinised every issue of the association's journal, *Der treudeutsche Hultschiner*, and did not permit RHH activities in the Hlučín region. The first arrests of individuals working for the RHH in the region occurred in 1922.⁴⁹ From 1923 onwards, membership of the RHH could be prosecuted under the Act for the Protection of the Republic, not only in the case of Czechoslovak citizens.⁵⁰ In late March 1926, seven optants were arrested in Czechoslovakia during visits to their former homes, despite holding Reich German passports, because they were members of the RHH. They were sentenced to four to seven weeks' imprisonment and subsequently expelled. In addition, a trial in Jihlava officially established, that Czechoslovak authorities regarded not only the RHH but also a number of other associations as irredentist. This case dealt mainly with Sudeten Germans. The German ambassador in Prague, Walter Koch, feared that a possible harsh Czechoslovak approach might serve as an

⁴⁵ Ibidem. The housing situation in Ratibor was extremely poor at the end of the year. According to an official report, there was a shortage of 4,198 flats. In 718 cases, two to three families were sharing a flat consisting of a kitchen and one room, while three to four persons were sharing one bed, according to the findings of a commission. Unsurprisingly, two thirds of these families were tubercular. A further 823 flats, mainly cellar flats, were entirely unsuitable and were to be closed for construction-police reasons. In addition, 624 families were living, or rather languishing, in spaces such as laundries, attics, and similar rooms without heating, cooking facilities, and water supply.

⁴⁶ Ibidem.

⁴⁷ ZAO, Reinhold Weigel, box 11, inv. no. 11.

⁴⁸ Moravský zemský archiv Brno (MZA), Zemský úřad Brno (ZÚB), box 198, file no. Res-21. For "obligatory" membership of the RHH, see also SOMMER, K.: *Proněmecké irredentistické hnutí*, p. 229.

⁴⁹ Národní archiv, Ministerstvo vnitra I – prezidium 225, box 1408, report on "Iredenta na Hlučínsku".

⁵⁰ This well-known Act No. 50/1923 Coll. was passed by the parliament following the assassination of Alois Rašín. Membership of the RHH was prosecuted under Section 17 concerning "association hostile to the state".

example for other states and worsen the situation of German minorities in other countries.

Consequently, a meeting on retaliatory measures against Czechoslovakia in connection with the Hlučín optants was held at the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (*Auswärtiges Amt*) in Berlin in June 1926. Among other options, participants considered reciprocal action against the Sokol organisation in Germany, but under German law, mere membership of that association did not constitute a criminal offence. Economic countermeasures were rejected, as Germany had a strong interest in the successful conclusion of ongoing negotiations on an economic agreement involving tariff reductions. The German side therefore refrained from publicising the case and limited its response to a diplomatic note and to Stresemann's letter to the Czechoslovak ambassador in Berlin, Kamil Krofta, in which the Minister of Foreign Affairs protested against the arrest and conviction of German citizens for membership of an association that was legal in Germany.⁵¹

The Czechoslovak government partially yielded. According to Krofta, two ministries, the Ministry of the Interior and the Ministry of Justice, instructed their subordinate authorities not to harass German citizens solely on the basis of membership of a German association, even if that association pursued irredentist aims against the Czechoslovak state, until the matter was finally resolved.⁵² A final settlement that would reflect German expectations was never reached. The Czechoslovak Ministry of Foreign Affairs maintained that the provisions of Section 17 of the 1923 Act for the Protection of the Republic⁵³ did not allow the government to guarantee that no Reich German would in future face prosecution for membership of a Reich German association with subversive tendencies towards Czechoslovakia. Such a guarantee would amount to a commitment not to apply a valid law. In July 1928, however, the Czechoslovak side emphasised that police and judicial authorities had been instructed not to take action against Reich Germans who did not engage in subversive activities merely on the grounds of their membership of a Reich German irredentist association. Any deviation by subordinate authorities would be addressed immediately.⁵⁴ After all, the Czechoslovak government had already promised such a distinction between passive members and perpetrators of subversive activity in March 1927, in its response to a German verbal note of 20 July 1926. The German ambassador Koch emphasised that although the arrangement did not fully meet German expectations, the Czechoslovak side was nevertheless fulfilling its commitments.⁵⁵

Returning to the activities of R. Weigel: even in later years, he remained involved in the placement of migrants from the Hlučín region, albeit on a smaller scale for understandable reasons. The motives for leaving Czechoslovakia, however, remained predominantly economic. In early 1933, propaganda by the German National Socialist Workers' Party (DNSAP) achieved notable success in the Hlučín region. Many young people joined the party, including ethnic Czechs with hostile attitudes towards Czechoslovakia. There were

⁵¹ Hauptstaatsarchiv Dresden, 10717 Ministerium der auswärtigen Angelegenheiten, 1872 Verhalten tschechischer Behörden gegen Mitglieder reichsdeutscher Deutschturnvereinigungen.

⁵² *Ibidem*, Berlin 23 July 1926, German Ministry of Foreign Affairs (*Auswärtiges Amt*) to the Saxon Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

⁵³ Section 17 of Act No. 50 of 19 March 1923 defined association hostile to the state.

⁵⁴ Hauptstaatsarchiv Dresden, 10717 Ministerium der auswärtigen Angelegenheiten, 1872 Verhalten tschechischer Behörden gegen Mitglieder reichsdeutscher Deutschturnvereinigungen, Berlin 14 July 1928, German Ministry of Foreign Affairs to the Saxon Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

⁵⁵ *Ibidem*, Prague 27 March 1927, report by the German ambassador Koch to Berlin.

cases of Hlučín inhabitants crossing the border into Germany, presenting party membership cards, and requesting employment and assistance on the grounds of alleged political persecution in Czechoslovakia. Some joined the NSDAP or even the SA in Germany. Others deliberately committed illegal acts in Czechoslovakia and then fled across the border, claiming political persecution.⁵⁶ For example, Bruno Postulka opened a convenience shop in Bohuslavice in spring 1935, but soon fell into debt owing to excessive expenditure. He decided to flee to Germany and make a fresh start. Intending to present himself as a martyr for Germanness, he fabricated “evidence” by placing a handwritten poster in his shop window, the content of which fulfilled the statutory definition of an offence under the Act for the Protection of the Republic. A few hours later, he reported to the first German border municipality. However, neither there nor later in Ratibor was he welcomed. He was told that such behaviour did not serve the Hlučín cause. Eventually, he was given a form to complete by the *Sudetendeutsche Kontrollstelle* in Dresden.

This office was established in December 1933, when German governmental authorities recognised that a growing number of so-called refugees were crossing the border for non-political reasons and constituted a burden on Germany, not to mention the danger of espionage. A control office was therefore created to examine all refugees from Czechoslovakia, i.e. not only Sudeten Germans but also Hlučín inhabitants, with regard to the credibility of their claims to assistance. In this examination, it was to be borne in mind that active fighters for the National Socialist cause were more needed in Czechoslovakia than in the Reich. Every refugee was required to complete a form and was investigated by the Dresden office. If the office did not issue a residence permit, the individual was expelled back.

Refugees from the Hlučín region evidently did not place a significant burden on this office, as the provincial president in Oppeln stated in March 1934 that there was no reason to establish a refugee commissioner’s office, since the number of refugees in the Oppeln province had not increased significantly in recent times.⁵⁷

Returning to Postulka’s case: only after the Dresden office recognised him as a political refugee did he receive residence and work permits. When an amnesty was declared, he returned home. However, as the amnesty covered only some of his offences, he was arrested for having fled to Germany. Since Czech authorities regarded the *Sudetendeutsche Kontrollstelle* as equivalent to the SA, he was sentenced to one year’s imprisonment and fined 1,000 crowns for contact with this organisation.⁵⁸

In October 1937, Weigel received clear instructions from the NSDAP regarding further departures from the Hlučín region and the criteria for recognising refugee status. Such status was to be granted only to party members endangered because of active work for the Sudeten German national group within a combat organisation if they had received a prison sentence exceeding six months; to party members who lacked means of subsistence as a result of punishment; and to compatriots (*Volksgenossen*) who were actively working in Germany’s interests and faced severe penalties as a consequence. Provocations and isolated actions were not to be taken into account.⁵⁹ Indeed, in September of the same year, following several escapes from the Hlučín region in the preceding weeks,

⁵⁶ Bundesarchiv Berlin-Lichterfelde, R 8043/960, file no. 3636/34.

⁵⁷ Hauptstaatsarchiv Dresden, 10717 Ministerium der auswärtigen Angelegenheiten, 1876 Kontrollstelle über sudetendeutsche Flüchtlinge.

⁵⁸ Bundesarchiv Berlin-Lichterfelde, R 8043/962, file no. 4037/36.

⁵⁹ *Ibidem*, R 8043/1552, file no. 3515/37.

Weigel himself stated that the impression must not be fostered among Hlučín inhabitants that they merely needed to be active for Germanness for a short time in order to flee to the Reich and secure a stable livelihood there.⁶⁰

During the 1930s, emigration from the Hlučín region also took place, very likely predominantly to Germany, although migration to the Ostrava region probably continued, like in the 1920s.⁶¹ This is evident from a comparison of the censuses in Hlučín municipalities in 1930 and 1939: the population declined by 1,777 persons,⁶² while natural increase between 1931 and 1937 amounted to 4,070. Although data for 1938 and the first four months of 1939 are unavailable, extrapolation suggests a further approximately 1,160 persons, i.e. a total of about 5,230 new inhabitants born between 1931 and April 1939.⁶³ Since the 1939 census recorded the total resident population (i.e. including absent persons), the decline cannot be attributed to the spring census date, when seasonal workers were already away from their homes, unlike the December 1930 census, which recorded only those present.

Commuters/Seasonal Workers – Pro-German Activity in the Hlučín Region as a Condition for Getting a Job in Germany

In addition to optants, the RHH was also involved in securing employment and the necessary permits for commuters and seasonal workers from the Hlučín region. In this case as well, the assistance was not motivated by altruism. The RHH's motivation stemmed from the association's objectives: the preservation of Germanness in the Hlučín region and, if possible, the return of the region to Germany. Individuals who received assistance were expected to vote for German political parties in the Hlučín region, subscribe to German newspapers, join German associations and organisations, and engage in pro-German agitation among their relatives and acquaintances. These expectations were well known. For obvious reasons, commuters and seasonal workers were far more useful for influencing conditions directly in the Hlučín region than optants.

It is therefore no coincidence that as early as 20 November 1920, barely three quarters of a year after the loss of the Hlučín region, the confidential senior government official August Wellenkamp in Oppeln informed Franz Peterka, chairman of the Association of Itinerant Traders in Kravaře and Kouty (*Verein der Wandergewerbetreibenden von Deutsch-Krawarn und Kauthen*), that the provincial president in Oppeln intended to permit former Reich Germans from the Hlučín region to continue operating itinerant trade in Germany.⁶⁴

However, the situation in Germany, particularly in Upper Silesia, was difficult in the early 1920s, and it was far from possible to absorb all the labour from the Hlučín region that had previously found employment there. Those who commuted to Germany for work

⁶⁰ Ibidem, file no. 3446/37, Oppeln 26 September 1937, Weigel wrote to the Deutsche Stiftung.

⁶¹ As noted above, the number of Hlučín inhabitants residing in the Ostrava region increased by more than 1,200 between 1921 and 1930.

⁶² *Sčítání lidu v Republice československé ze dne 1. prosince 1930*, 1. Praha 1934, p. 20; *Amtliches Gemeindeverzeichnis für das Grossdeutsche Reich auf Grund der Volkszählung 1939*. Berlin 1944, p. 97; BINAR, Aleš: *Hospodářský a sociální vývoj Hlučínska v letech 1945–1989*. Opava 2014, p. 42. Natural population increase in the Hlučín district between the 1921 and 1930 censuses amounted to 7,591 persons, while net migration loss totalled 4,181 persons.

⁶³ Data on natural population change for individual districts are available on the website of the Czech Statistical Office.

⁶⁴ ZAO, Reinhold Weigel, box 3.

were affected by the depreciation of the mark, which made it difficult for them to maintain their families in Czechoslovakia on their earnings.⁶⁵

The surviving materials contain several testimonies about the placement activities of Dr Reinhold Weigel or “his” RHH. In 1926, the trade union secretary in Gleiwitz (Gliwice), Franz Heidrich, evidently on the basis of prior correspondence, informed Weigel that, despite the poor state of the construction market, it was possible to place 19 bricklayers from the Hlučín municipalities of Rohov and Strahovice with the Brieger company in Bobrek (a part of Beuthen). Heidrich also expressed confidence that it would soon be possible to place several more individuals from the municipalities of Bělá and Kravaře who had significantly engaged in favour of Germanness during elections. According to Heidrich’s statistics, 268 workers from the Hlučín region were employed in Gleiwitz and its surroundings at that time.⁶⁶ Although the preceding correspondence has not survived, it may be assumed that Weigel directly asked Heidrich to secure jobs for pro-German activists from the Hlučín region as a reward for their activities.

In 1927, Weigel informed Erich Kraemer-Möllenberg, the leading figure in the *Deutsche Stiftung*, about the situation of the unemployed from the Hlučín region. He proudly reported that his organisation (i.e. the RHH) had already helped itself through self-help. The Christian trade unions in Gleiwitz, with which he was in contact, were making every effort to place Hlučín bricklayers who had previously worked there. He further stated that agricultural labourers from the Hlučín region had also been successfully placed.⁶⁷ In the same year, Weigel was forced to resign from the chairmanship of the RHH after the Czech side declared, during negotiations on facilitating cross-border contact between the Hlučín and Opava regions and the Lower Silesian province, that it would regard it as unacceptable for a German government official to head the RHH. Nevertheless, Weigel remained intensively active in Hlučín matters, among other things through his activities within the *Deutsche Stiftung*.⁶⁸

There is unequivocal evidence of direct pressure on Hlučín inhabitants seeking employment in Germany. When Jan Bortlík, a locksmith from the municipality of Koberčice, was prosecuted by Czechoslovak authorities in 1925 for membership of the RHH, he stated the following as a mitigating circumstance: after completing primary school, he worked as a locksmith in the Hlučín region in 1920–1924, but then he lost his job and was unable to find employment in Czechoslovakia. He therefore travelled to Ratibor, where he was told that, as a Hlučín inhabitant, he should contact the RHH. He went to see his former teacher, Hermann Janosch,⁶⁹ who encouraged him to become a member of the RHH, explaining that only as a member would he be able to work in Germany, whereas otherwise he would not be tolerated as a foreigner. Bortlík paid the membership fee, and Janosch issued him with a membership card and a certificate confirming his German nationality.

⁶⁵ Bundesarchiv Berlin-Lichterfelde, R 1501/105818, Bandnummer 1, Hultschiner Ländchen Nov. 1922 – Okt. 1927 Aktenzeichen, a cutting of R. Weigel’s article in Volkswille of 28 July 1922.

⁶⁶ ZAO, Reinhold Weigel, box 6. It is not evident from the numerical figure whether it included only seasonal workers, i.e. Czechoslovak citizens, or also optants, i.e. German citizens originating from the Hlučín region.

⁶⁷ Bundesarchiv Berlin-Lichterfelde, R 8043/958, file no. 6402/1927, Weigel’s letter dated 19 August 1927.

⁶⁸ *Ibidem*, Weigel’s letter dated 15 May 1927.

⁶⁹ Janosch came from Ludgeřovice and worked as a teacher in Koberčice until 1920. After the annexation of the Hlučín region by Czechoslovakia, he opted for Germany. He became Weigel’s most important colleague and the executive chairman of the RHH association. DOKOUPIL, L. – MYŠKA, M. (eds.): *Biografický slovník*, p. 49.

Then he obtained employment in Prussian Silesia.⁷⁰

According to information held by Czechoslovak police authorities, the majority of itinerant traders from Kravaře and Kouty working in Germany in the late 1920s (approximately 400 at that time) were members of the RHH or at least in close contact with the organisation. They were expected to engage in agitation at the organisation's instruction prior to elections.⁷¹ The police suspected Richard Thiemel, a peasant from Kravaře, of submitting written reports to the RHH on citizens originating from Kouty who were employed in Germany, as did Josef Slaný from Kravaře, who allegedly provided information to the German passport office in Moravská Ostrava.⁷²

The aforementioned Slaný was the secretary of the German Christian Socialists in Kravaře. Czechoslovak police authorities concluded that he was paid by Reich German authorities to provide testimonials about all Hlučín inhabitants whose livelihoods depended on employment in Germany, particularly bricklayers and itinerant traders. The Police Directorate in Opava possessed photocopies of enquiries sent by German authorities to Slaný concerning the suitability of Josef Urbisch, a locksmith from Kravaře applying for German citizenship; Alois Waschütz, who had applied for support from the Reich branch for war-disabled persons; and František Pawlík, who was seeking a residence permit in Germany.⁷³

The suspicions of the Czechoslovak authorities were well founded. Archival sources produced by the activities of the Deutsche Stiftung demonstrate that Josef Slaný was an informant for the German consulates in Moravská Ostrava and Brno.⁷⁴ In 1937, when Slaný was already residing in Germany, Weigel endeavoured to secure employment for him in Hamburg or Bremen.⁷⁵

During the Great Depression, unemployment in the Hlučín region rose rapidly. As a result, people increasingly pinned their hopes on the possibility of working in Germany. Czechoslovak authorities were aware that the employment of Hlučín inhabitants in Germany worsened the already difficult prospects for the integration of the Hlučín region into the Czechoslovak Republic. The problem intensified after Hitler's rise to power in 1933, when seasonal workers were exposed not only to German, but directly to National Socialist indoctrination. On 14 November 1933, the District Office in Hlučín requested the Provincial Office in Brno that agricultural labourers from the Hlučín region should not be sent to Germany in the following year, unlike in 1933, when approximately 1,000 individuals, primarily women, had travelled on permits. Nevertheless, in early April 1934, demonstrations took place in Hlučín demanding permission for departures for

⁷⁰ MZA, ZÚB, box 198, statement by Jan Bortlík, taken on 17 September 1925.

⁷¹ According to Vilém Plaček, there were approximately 600 such itinerant traders in Kravaře in 1923. From the late 1920s onwards, conditions for itinerant trade were tightened in Germany as well. The German consulate in Moravská Ostrava vetted applicants on the basis of their pro-German attitudes. In autumn 1929, it screened approximately 450 applications of itinerant traders. The stricter conditions and sales problems during the Great Depression led to a decline in itinerant trade in Kravaře. PLÁČEK, V.: *Prajáci 2*, pp. 63–64.

⁷² MZA, ZÚB, box 198, file no. Res – 37/4, 20 March 1929, report by the Police Directorate in Opava to the Presidium of the Provincial Office in Opava.

⁷³ *Ibidem*, box 134, file no. 71 dův., Provincial Gendarmerie Headquarters for Silesia, Kravaře station, 7 September 1928; and file no. Res. 198/5, Police Directorate in Opava, 2 October 1928, regarding Slaný's suspicious contacts with Reich German authorities.

⁷⁴ Bundesarchiv Berlin-Lichterfelde, R 8043/1550.

⁷⁵ *Ibidem*, R 8043/963.

work in Germany. Under pressure from the unemployed population, the state authorities relented, and 1,232 agricultural workers departed in 1934. In 1937, 2,736 adults from eighteen municipalities of the Hlučín region, with a total population of 35,772, received permission to travel to Germany for work.⁷⁶ Taking into account other sectors (itinerant trade, construction, etc.), the highest proportions of seasonal workers in Germany in 1937 came from Kravaře and Kouty (21% and 27% of the population, respectively). It is no coincidence that these two municipalities consistently exhibited the strongest dominance of German political parties in elections.⁷⁷

According to Hermann Janosch's data, trained bricklayers, craftsmen, and traders were also included in the transports of agricultural workers in 1937. It appears that, under severe economic conditions, even men did not disdain lower-paid agricultural work in order to maintain their families. The target destination was predominantly the Hannover region. Janosch appealed for local branches of the Federation of the German East (*Bund deutscher Osten*) to engage in ideological work with seasonal labourers from the Hlučín region.⁷⁸

Memories of parents working in Germany were also recalled by contemporary witnesses from the Hlučín region whose testimonies have been collected by the Museum of the Hlučín Region.⁷⁹ Anna Gajdová's father would commute for work to the Rybník region. Every morning, he would walk from Darkovice to the train station in Annaberg (nowadays Chaľupki) to continue by train to the mine, where he worked as a bricklayer. She herself remembers travelling to the Hannover region from 1934 onwards to earn money as a seasonal agricultural worker. Hedvika Lasáková from Píšť, whose father also travelled to Germany for work as a bricklayer, spent three seasons employed in German agriculture – in Saxony, Thuringia, and Mecklenburg. She was recruited by an agent who initially resided in Ratibor and later moved directly to the Hlučín region, to Kravaře. Lidvína Krejzková from Kobeřice stated that her father had worked in Germany as a commuter and returned home only at weekends.

In 1936, Czechoslovak authorities reported the following with regard to bricklayers from the Hlučín region seeking employment in Germany: *At the end of last year, upon the return of the bricklayer Jan Macháček, it was found that the named individual was in possession of various official documents from which it was evident that Macháček stood at the forefront of the German movement in the Hlučín region. Thus, Macháček possessed a notification from the local authority that he had been removed from his position as a substitute member of the municipal council in Hněvošice under Act No. 201/33; that under the same Act, he had been placed under police surveillance; that at one time, he had been the chairman of the local branch of the DNSAP, etc. Macháček had procured German translations of these documents. In addition, he was in possession of a party membership card of the SdP. During an interrogation by the local authority, Macháček admitted that he had taken the SdP membership card and the official documents with him to Germany in order to be able to demonstrate there that he was at the forefront of the German movement in the Hlučín region in the event that he encountered any difficulties in Germany [...] It was also found that bricklayers from the Hlučín region who intend to seek work in Germany are*

⁷⁶ PLÁČEK, V.: *Prajzáci* 2, pp. 187, 200.

⁷⁷ KÁŇA, Otakar: Sociálně ekonomická a organizační základna německého iredentismu na Hlučínsku. *Slezský sborník* 64, 1966, 3, pp. 306–317, here p. 315.

⁷⁸ Bundesarchiv Berlin-Lichterfelde, R 8043/1552.

⁷⁹ Complete audio recordings are available in the research room of the Museum of the Hlučín Region.

withdrawing from Czech associations, apparently so that membership of a Czech association does not constitute an obstacle when seeking employment in Germany. Among these are also individuals of Moravian orientation,⁸⁰ who are, however, compelled to act in this manner by prolonged unemployment.⁸¹

Conclusion

In 1928, Josef Šrámek, the former Plenipotentiary Commissioner for the Hlučín Region (the office having been abolished a year earlier), stated that *the faith of the simple Hlučín populace, who are neither nationally nor politically conscious, in the power of the association Reichsverband heimatliebender Hultschiner is very strong, as the association provides them with tangible material benefits by enabling them to earn money in Germany in gold marks, or at least by promising such advantages. Given the current exchange rate between our crown and the Reichsmark, this form of irredentism is undoubtedly the most effective, especially when one takes into account the pronounced opportunism of the Hlučín population.*⁸² Shortly thereafter, the already difficult integration of the Hlučín region into Czechoslovakia suffered a severe blow with the onset of the Great Depression. It was precisely this crisis that enabled the successful offensive of German irredentists. The functionaries of the RHH were aware of the key role played by the arrangement of employment opportunities in maintaining influence in the Hlučín region.

Šrámek's condemnation of Hlučín opportunism may be somewhat overly harsh and perhaps also reflects an element of village rivalry: Šrámek was born in Štítina, barely two kilometres from Kravaře, yet on the right bank of the Opava River, which had separated Austria from Prussia until 1920. The inhabitants of *Hlučínsko* can hardly be reproached for taking advantage of every opportunity to maintain their families in the context of high unemployment. They did not wish to join the Czechoslovak Republic, and the subsequent difficulties in finding employment in the new state strengthened their belief that the imposed change of state was a mistake. Employment in Germany indisputably further reinforced the already positive relationship of the Hlučín population to the former homeland. However, when obtaining jobs in Germany, they knew "the rules of the game": active pro-German activity was a condition. Therefore, they must have realised that they were being used within the framework of political struggle.

Unfortunately, Germany came under the control of a perverted ideology in the 1930s. In October 1938, the Hlučín region returned to Germany for six and a half years. The population felt that they had returned home, to the *Heimat*. A year later, war broke out and Hlučín men, as German citizens, once again set out on their journeys, this time, however, in uniform. Approximately 3,500 to 4,000 of them perished in the war (not including optants).

The inhabitants of the Hlučín region undoubtedly paid a price for their attachment to Germany. Since the second half of the 20th century, family memory in the Hlučín region has concentrated on its own hard fates: men killed while serving in the Wehrmacht, women and girls raped by Red Army soldiers, material damage suffered during the fighting, the difficult living conditions of incomplete families in the immediate post-war years,

⁸⁰ By this term, Czechoslovak authorities meant people loyal to the state.

⁸¹ MZA, ZÚB, box 245, file no. 2726/36.

⁸² Národní archiv, Ministerstvo vnitra I – prezidium 225, box 1408, report on "Iredenta na Hlučínsku", f. 55.

and the distrust of Czech society towards people who had fought in both world wars on the “wrong side” and spoke a dialect saturated with Germanisms. As a native of the Hlučín region, I recall hearing statements from older people such as: *We did not know what Hitler was really like and that he wanted war.*⁸³ This self-stylisation as victims prevents posing crucial questions: is ignorance an excuse? Is it possible to distinguish between Nazism and Germany in the 1930s?

As decade followed decade, time softened the sharpest edges. Hlučín inhabitants focused on building family houses and cultivating their small plots or gardens. Communist economic materialism, with its emphasis on heavy industry, in certain respects aligned with their industriousness and focus on the material aspects of life. In 1961, 69% of the economically active population commuted to work outside their place of permanent residence, mostly to Ostrava and partly to Opava.⁸⁴ In 1988, 73% of the economically active population of the Hlučín part of the Opava district commuted for work, three quarters of them to Ostrava. By that time, several municipalities of the former Hlučín region had already become part of the Ostrava-město district.⁸⁵ Earnings in Ostrava’s heavy industry were above average. The construction and expansion of industrial enterprises in the Ostrava and Karviná regions enabled inhabitants from *Hlučínsko* to find employment within an hour’s travel distance from home. Their interwar problems with unemployment disappeared during the times of the communist dictatorship. Their social security increased in a non-democratic political regime.

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⁸³ The historian Vilém Plaček aptly entitled the fifth chapter of the second volume of *Prajázci* “Abused by Henlein”. See PLAČEK, V.: *Prajázci* 2.

⁸⁴ BINAR, A.: *Hospodářský a sociální vývoj*, p. 265.

⁸⁵ *Ibidem*, p. 266.

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